

DEVELOPMENT OF COOPERATION CULTURE IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: This article addresses the issue of developing a culture of collaboration in preschool education organizations. The culture of collaboration in preschool education should be established not only between educators and parents but also among various departments of educational organizations, society, and the state. The article discusses the importance of a collaborative culture, the main directions of its development, and the need for decision-making to strengthen relationships among educators. Additionally, the article analyzes the existing model of collaborative culture and provides practical recommendations for its improvement.

Keywords: preschool education, culture of collaboration, educators, society, decisions, pedagogical development, education policy, collaboration with parents.

Introduction

The preschool education system plays an important role in shaping the future of society. As the initial stage of children's intellectual, emotional and social development, quality education and upbringing in preschool education are of great importance.

Today, the preschool education system is not limited to the implementation of pedagogical activities alone. It is also developing in line with social, cultural and economic changes in society. In this regard, the issue of developing a culture of cooperation in preschool educational organizations is particularly important, as this process not only increases the effectiveness of the educational process, but also serves to improve the social environment.

Preschool educational organizations play an important role in creating a more developmental, safe and friendly environment for children by establishing effective cooperation between educators, parents, society and the state.

Developing a culture of cooperation not only has a positive impact on the educational and upbringing process, but also allows for improving the overall quality of the education system, joint problem solving and strengthening social responsibility. In this case, all aspects of cooperation should be organized on the basis of mutual trust and respect between educators, parents, society and the state.

The article discusses the importance of a culture of cooperation in the preschool education system, the main directions of its development, decisions to be made and practical recommendations for establishing cooperation. At the same time, directions for measuring the effectiveness of a culture of cooperation, evaluating its results and developing it are given.

The main focus is on how a culture of cooperation can benefit all participants in the education system and create a quality educational environment for children.

A culture of cooperation is a system of social relations that develops on the basis of mutual trust, respect and solidarity between subjects at different levels in the education system. A culture of cooperation in preschool educational organizations means establishing

and developing relationships between teachers, parents, society and the state. The main goal of cooperation is to improve the quality of education through mutually beneficial and positive relationships, to create better development conditions for children.

The development of a culture of cooperation is especially important in the preschool education system. This process helps to improve the skills of teachers, improve the quality of communication with parents and increase the attention of society to education.

A culture of cooperation in preschool educational organizations, in turn, affects the development of children, their social and emotional well-being.¹

To develop a culture of cooperation in the preschool education system, the following key decisions should be made:

Strengthening relationships between teachers. Good relationships and exchange of experiences between teachers increase the effectiveness of the educational process. For this, seminars, conferences and trainings should be held in educational organizations. This will allow teachers to learn new pedagogical methods, solve educational problems and use modern technologies.

Strengthening cooperation with parents. Cooperation with parents is necessary to create the best development environment for children. It is necessary to ensure constant communication between parents and educational organizations, joint work in solving problems and active participation of children in the educational process. Preschool educational organizations should regularly organize meetings, consultations and educational events with parents.

Cooperation with society and the state. Preschool educational organizations should develop relations with society and establish cooperation to effectively manage the requirements imposed on the education system by the state and financial resources. It is necessary to increase the social responsibility of the education system, to work together to solve social issues related to education in society. Cooperation with society contributes to the improvement of the education system, the introduction of new pedagogical technologies.

Effective distribution of resources. For the effective distribution of resources in the education system, it is necessary to develop cooperation between teachers and educational organizations. The effectiveness of education can be increased by optimizing resources, including financial and time resources. The role of society in attracting resources for preschool educational organizations should be significant.

Pedagogical training and advanced training. It is necessary to organize continuous advanced training courses and seminars for teachers. This will allow teachers to learn new pedagogical methods, improve the educational process, and use modern technologies.

It also creates an opportunity for teachers to share their knowledge and skills with others by establishing mutual exchange of experiences between educational organizations.

Harmonization of educational programs and innovative approaches. Preschool educational organizations should focus on harmonizing educational programs and methodologies. To do this, it is necessary to develop effective mechanisms for cooperation

¹ Xudoyberganova, N. (2020). Pedagogical innovations in preschool education. Tashkent: O'quvchi.

and exchange of experience between educators. Developing programs based on innovative approaches creates better educational opportunities for children.

Use of technologies. With the help of modern technologies, it is possible to effectively manage the educational process and strengthen ties between educational organizations. With the help of online platforms and electronic resources, it is possible to cooperate more effectively between teachers and parents. In addition, technologies allow the use of innovative methods in the education of children. Various methodological approaches can be used to measure the effectiveness of the culture of cooperation in preschool educational organizations. These measurements cover the following main areas:

Pedagogical exchange. The level of exchange of experience and knowledge among teachers.

Communication with parents. Measuring the effectiveness of communication with parents, assessing their participation in the educational process.

Resources and opportunities. The level of effective management and distribution of available resources and opportunities of educational organizations.

One of the main results of developing a culture of cooperation is the creation of a high-quality and successful educational environment for children.

Pedagoglar o'rtasidagi samarali hamkorlik bolalarning individual ehtiyojlarini qondirishda va ularning rivojlanishiga xizmat qilishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Ota-onalar bilan samarali hamkorlik esa, bolalarning ijtimoiy va emosional holatini yaxshilaydi. Shuningdek, jamiyat bilan o'zaro aloqalar ta'lim tizimining ijtimoiy jihatdan maqbul va samarali bo'lishiga olib keladi.

Measurement element	Description
Pedagogical exchange	Exchange of experience and knowledge between educators
Communication with parents	Regular meetings and events with parents
Communication with the community	Strengthening cooperation with society and the state
Development programs	Development of special programs for education and development

Table: Key dimensions of a collaborative culture in preschool educational organizations

Conclusion

Developing a culture of cooperation in the preschool education system is a very important and wide-ranging process, which is not limited only to relations between teachers. The development of a culture of cooperation in preschool educational organizations not only improves the quality of the pedagogical process, but also serves to strengthen ties between society, parents and the state.

Exchange of experience between teachers, establishment of effective relations with parents, and active cooperation with society help create a comfortable, safe and developing environment for children.

In the process of developing a culture of cooperation, educational organizations should not forget about the need to create a positive environment for cooperation.

To ensure open communication, mutual assistance, and openness to suggestions between teachers, special trainings and seminars are required, as well as the introduction of new pedagogical technologies.

Relations with parents directly affect the development of children, therefore educational organizations should establish constant cooperation with parents.

Partnership with the community also has a positive impact on the quality of education, as it helps to solve social issues related to education in society. Strengthening relationships and agreements helps to expand the capabilities of preschool educational organizations and effectively allocate resources.

In addition, the development of partnership in preschool education includes not only short-term, but also long-term effects.

This contributes to the mental, physical and social development of children, as well as the establishment of strong social ties in society. By establishing a culture of partnership, educators, parents and society together achieve an improvement in the quality of children's education.

Therefore, the issue of developing a culture of partnership in the preschool education system is very important not only for increasing the effectiveness of education, but also for ensuring the future development of society. In implementing this process, mutual respect, trust and harmony of mutual interests of all parties should be the main factors.

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